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**Performance of parasitoid *Bracon hebetor* (Say.)
(Hymenoptera: Braconidae) Rearing on two Lepidopteran
Host *Plodia interpunctella* Hübner and *Corcyra
cephalonica* Stainton**

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Chapter One

General Introduction

1. Indian meal moth

The Indian meal moth, *Plodia interpunctella* (Hübner) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) is a serious pest of various stored manufactured products (Simmons and Nelson, 1975). It is a cosmopolitan pest of food storage facilities, and can infest a variety of nuts, spices, and food products (Mohandass et al., 2007)

Padia interpunctella (Hübner) is a major economic insect pest of stored products and is found on every continent except Antarctica (Ress, 2004). *Padia interpunctella* has been found within parasitized commodities in commercial ocean freight shipments (Schulten and Roorda, 1984) and in food products imported into the United Kingdom from Africa (Cox, 1979).

2. Rice Moth

Corcyra cephalonica (Stainton), pyralid moth of the family (Galleriidae); order lepidoptera is a destructive and cosmopolitan storage pest (Neupane, 2000). It predominantly attacks or rice; so it is commonly named as 'rice moth' or 'rice meal moth' contrary to its name, *C. cephalonica* not only attack on rice but also in wheat, corn, sorghum, groundnut, cotton seeds, coffee, spices and cocoa beans (Allotey, 1986; Kumar and Kamar, 2001; Ayyar, 1934). The rice moth is firmly built, dirty grey with hairs fringing the lower edges of fore and hindwings. The moths are nocturnal and eggs are laid indiscriminately anywhere on the bags, godowns and wall. Infestations of *Podia interpunctella* can cause direct product loss and indirect economic costs through pest control costs, quality losses and consumer complaints (Chillips et al., 2000).

Pest control is an acceptable and necessary part of modern agriculture and is required for increasing crop production. There are various types of methods followed for controlling pest including chemical control, physical control, biological control of pests.

Numerous insecticides have been used to control Indian meal moth population, but effectiveness is limited. In a study evaluating the effectiveness of an insect growth regulator. It was found that even after treatment with these chemicals Indian meal moths were in corn storage bins. Resistance also was observed in studies performed with the microbial insecticide *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Resistance was just as likely with exposure to single strains of as with mixtures of sequences of the insecticide. Biological control promises to be an important componesnt of integrated pest management strategies for many types of stored commodities. Biological control agent included pathogens, Parasitoids, and predators. The use of natural enemies is considered as a useful alternative method for the control of stored products pests as well as agricultural and medical pests (Press et al. 1982; Hujek, 2004; Yu et al., 2003).

Among the various groups of biocontrol agents braconoid parasitoids are well known for the management of different pest insects. The braconoid wasp *Bracon hebetor* (say) is an ectoparasitoid that attacks larvae of several species of lepidoptepra, mainly pyralid moths. It is an important biological control agents of stored product moth (Broueer et al., 1996) especially those infesting stored in various parts of the world.

Chapter Two

Review of Literature

A general description of all life stages of *P. interpunctella* was first given by Hamlin et al, (1931) and there are several more recent summaries and descriptions (Rees, 2004). Detailed morphological descriptions of larvae, pupae and adults were given in Richards and Thomson (1932) and in Hinton (1943), and Heinrich (1956) describes about wing venation and genitalia of the sexes, there are five larval instars (Allotey and Goswami, 1990). Arbogast et al. (1980) describes the eggs of *P. interpunctella* as being small, with rounded excrescences and prominent carinae, and give a key for separating the eggs from those of other common stored product insects.

Oviposition decisions by female lepidopterous insects can be crucial for the survival of their offspring mainly because the neonate larvae of some species are relatively immobile, and absence of an immediate optional food resource could be detrimental to the development of the larvae and fitness of the adults, (Thompson and Pellmyr, 1991). Oviposition behavior in *P. interpunctella* is influenced by food odor (Phillips and Strand, 1994) and eggs are laid on or near the food surface, often spatially aggregated in some fashion (Mullen and Arbogast, 1977; Arbogast and Mullen, 1978) Phillips and Strand (1994) found that adult *P. interpunctella* oriented towards food odors and laid more eggs on substrates containing food than on those without food, and more eggs were laid on dishes that contained conspecific larval secretions.

The presence of oils can also lead to an increase in oviposition of *P. interpunctella* (Nansen and Phillips, 2003). Fecundity of *P. interpunctella* differs greatly from one study to another and is dependent upon several

factors, such as type of food, size of the female, provision of drinking water, and physiological state of the female moths (Mbata, 1985).

Mbata (1985) reported that maximum fecundity occurred at 30°C, Bell (1975) documents successful breeding but not maximum fecundity at 30°C, and Johnson et al. (1992, 1995) show egg laying up to 31°C, dependent in part on the rearing diet. The food source is obviously an important factor for determining fecundity and other biological parameters. Allotey and Goswami (1990) recorded mean fecundities of 174.2 on wheat and 174.2 on broken maize, which are much lower than the mean fecundities of 258, 275 and 280 when the young larvae were reared on walnuts, almonds, and wheat bran, respectively (Johnson et al, 1992).

The use of natural products to control various stored-product insects, including *P. interpunctella* is an alternative to chemical treatments and fumigation (Arthur, 1996). Biological control is a bioeffective-method of controlling pests (including insects, mites, weeds and plant diseases) using other living organisms (Flint and Steve, 1998). *Bracon hebetor* (Say) an ecto-larval parasitoid is considered as one of the most important biological control agents. It plays an important role to control almost all of the lepidopteran insect pests. This parasitoid has also reported as efficient biocontrol agent of *P. interpunctella*. The biology of *B. hebetor* has been intensively studied because of its importance as a biological control agent of the moths and also it is easy to rear in the laboratory (Benson, 1973; Taylor, 1988; Brower and Press, 1990; Heimpel et al., 1997; Baker and Fabric, 2000; Darwish et al, 2003; Giindiiz and Gulel, 2005; Milonas, 2005; Magro et al, 2006; Gundiiz et al, 2008). For insect parasitoids an individual host is the entire larval food source. So, both the number of other larvae with which a host shared, and host size, stage or species, can affect the development time, size, survival and fecundity of parasitoids (Corrigan et al, 1995; Gul

and Gulel, 1995; Ueno, 1999a,b; Harbison et al, 2001; Rohne, 2002; Giindiiz and Gulel, 2004, 2005; Milonas, 2005).

Female *B. hebetor* can produce eggs without host-feeding, suggesting that it stores nutrients during larval feeding and when food is not available, energy resources \ and up in eggs, fat body or muscle tissue can be converted into usable energy.

In recent years many researchers have studied the effects of host quality and or quantity on biology and ecology of *B. hebetor* (Ullyett, 1945; Douth, 1959; Taylor, 1988; Yu et al, 2003). Eliopoulos and Stathas (2008), for instance, investigated the life table parameters of *B. hebetor* parasitising *Anagasta kuehniella* Zeller 1879 (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) and *P. interpunctella* (Hiibner, 1813) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). Their work was based on the comparison of parasitoid's life table parameters related to those of its hosts at various conditions of host density. Yu et al. (2003) reported the Effects of host density on egg dispersion and the sex ratio of *B. hebetor*.

In parasitoid density experiments, a density of ten male-female pairs of *B. hebetor* produced a higher number of progeny on 50 last instar GWM larvae. Similarly, in a host density experiment, a density of 60 last instars GWM larvae produced a significantly higher number of parasitoid progeny followed by 50 last instar GWM larvae among the tested host densities when two pairs of *B. hebetor* were used. The sex ratio of the progenies was male-biased in these studies and there were no significant effects on sex ratio from variation in host density and parasitoid density. (Alam et al., 2016)

Host species had a small but significant effect on mean development time of *B. hebetor* but host density had no significant effects on it (Taylor, 1988). The longevity of females did not show any noteworthy change with host Density, whereas it showed some variations in males (Isitan et al, 2011)

B. hebetor females adjust clutch size based on host density. Previous studies reported that when a female *B. hebetor* wasp supplied with only one host

larva every day, it never lays more than 7 or 12 eggs per host (Milonas and Savopoulou- Soutani, 1999; Yu et al., 2003).

AIM OF THE WORK

The primary goal of this project was to assess the performance of parasitoid *Bracon hebetor* (Say.) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) reared on two lepidopteran host Indian meal moth *Plodia interpunctella* Hübner and rice moth *Corcyra cephalonica* Stainton.

The present experiments were carried out on the following aspects:

- to assess the parasitism percent in *B. hebetor* rearing *P. interpunctella* and *C. cephalonica* .
- to estimate the growth and development of *B. hebetor* rearing *P. interpunctella* and *C. cephalonica* .

CHAPTER THREE

Mass Rearing of Host Indian meal Moth *Plodia interpunctella* and Parasitoid *Bracon hebetor*

Mass Rearing of Indian meal Moth *Plodia interpunctella*

3.1 Introduction:

Mass and laboratory rearing insect is a key component of several integrated pest management strategies. However mass or laboratory rearing can have dramatic effects on insect performance via laboratory adaptation, inbreeding depression, inadvertent selection or through direct rearing effects (e.g. crowding and artificial diets). Thus, when rearing insects intended for field release, or when research is intended to reflect wild population performance; there is a need to establish quality under these conditions. In reality however, much of the focus on reality control of mass or laboratory reared insect concerns maintenance of facility output (i.e. numbers) to a much lesser extent, individual trait effects (e.g. mating competitiveness or field flight performance). This is due to practical issues (time or budget constraints), but also to limited understanding of the relationship between laboratory and field assays and the basic biology of the species.

Entomophagous insect may present problems for mass rearing. If entomophages have not been before these insects much often be reared on the natural host or prey since no artificial diet has been created as a result, the laboratory rearing of beneficial insects encompasses three entities: the beneficial species, the insect host, and the plant host or artificial food. Maintaining all the three levels can be difficult and in some cases costly.

The concept of mass production may be defined as the skilful and highly refined processing of an entomophagous species and its host substrate through sectary

producer which result in the economic production of large numbers of beneficial insects. Rearing of beneficial insect's ecomphases the synchronization of three biological entities the beneficial species, the host species, and the host plant or food. The goal of a mass production programme is to produce the maximum labour, space and cost. This may be through standardization of procedure, mechanization of the programme, efficient production, and maintenance of quality control; effective sanitation and microbial control contamination in the rearing laboratory (singh, 1982).

The important qualities required in a laboratory reared insect are short life cycle, high biotic potential, simple food requirement, and alternative hosts. Quality control of mass product insects currently includes a number of interrelated but not yet unified concepts. Entomophagous insects have been reared in large numbers for some time now. However, mass production began some 36 years ago after the introduction of the concepts of genetic control. During the early 1970s general concepts with which to evaluate and improve the quality of insects produced at lowest costs were virtually non-existent. It was not until the late 1970s that concepts of quality control emerged. Quality of mass reared insect is generally defined and measured in terms of how will the insect population functions in its intended role, either in the field or laboratory (Huttel, 1976).

Several traits related to quality of laboratory reared insects are listed and include vigour, activity, reproductive potential and biotic potential. Some of the changes that may affect quality are alternations in metabolic functions or nutritional. Reserve content, tolerance to temperature, and toxins. Other factors are fertility, fecundity, longevity, and changes in biological conformity such as rhythm mating behaviour and host specificity (Singh 1982). The present study has been undertaken to develop a mass rearing of Indian meal moth *P. interpunctella* at the laboratory condition.

3.2 Materials and Methods

Culture of host

Insect colony: A laboratory culture of *Plodia interpunctella* was used for this experiment. Our initial *P. interpunctella* culture was obtained from the post-harvest Entomology laboratory, Department of zoology, Rajshahi University. This laboratory culture was from adults collected from the local food facilities located at Rajshahi metro politan city. They were reared on maize flour under laboratory condition at 27°C degree Celsius and 70-75% RH at the Post Harvest Entomology laboratory, Department of Zoology, Rajshahi University.

Culture box: For this experiment plastic boxes were used. The size of the boxes was L-14.0, W-11.2 cm and H-8.50 cm. the boxes were obtained from the local market. As the lid of the box very small mesh sized net was used, this system allowed easy gaseous exchange. The gap between lid and plastic boxes were scaled carefully so that not a single larva can come outside from the culture box.

Diet: Maize flour was used as the food of *P. intertpunctella*. The maize seed was collected from the market, and then dried in under sunlight, after that we cruised the seed and made flour. The flour was again heated in 50 degree Celsius for 24 hours in an Incubator for disinfecting it. After cooling down, this flour was used as food in mass culture box. The thickness of the food was 2 inches.

Adult release: 50 pairs of adults 950 male and 50 female *P. interpunctella*) were released in each mass culture box. All the adults were fresh and newly hatched. We used tissue papers so that adults can easily sit and lay eggs on it. Each female laid eggs for 3 days. Male died soon after mating and female dies after finishing egg lying. When the last adult died in the mass culture box then we removed the dead bodies carefully from the boxes.

Cellulae: Newly emerged virgin males (age less than one hr) were paired with 1–3 days old virgin females (treatments 4–6). Each treatment was replicated 10 times by introducing the moths in glass jars (10×5 cm). After insect pairing, jars were covered with small pieces of muslin cloth. The glass jars were checked daily for

number of eggs laid by females after sieving through the eggs from diet. The longevity of adults was recorded until all adults were dead.

Egg collection: Collected eggs were placed daily in Petri dishes of size 25×10 mm along with rearing diet. : Eggs of the Indian meal moth appear greyish white and range in length from 0.3 to 0.5 mm. Eggs are oviposited singly or in clusters, and are generally laid directly on the larval food source.

Larval collection: There are five to seven larval instars. Their color is usually off-white, but has been observed to be pink, brown or almost greenish, depending on the food source. They have five pairs of well-developed pro-legs that help them move considerable distances to pupate. After 25 days of releasing adults in the mass culture box mature larva was collected from the food and there weight was measured. For calculating to total larva number statistically. The size of each spots was 2 inch.

Pupae: The larvae pupate either in a silken cocoon or unprotected. The pupae are 1/4 to 2/5 inch long (6 to 11 mm) and are pale brown in color. Pupation takes place away from the infested material. In fact, late instar larvae can travel such distances that they are often mistaken for clothing pests. Within the pantry, small larvae often climb to other shelves before pupating. This misleads people trying to find the source of the infestation.

Adult collection: Adults are about 1/2 inch (12.7 mm) long with a wing span of about 5/8 inch (16 to 20 mm). The forewings of this moth are reddish brown with a copper sheen on the outer two thirds and grey on the inner third. At rest the wings are held roof-like over the body. The head and thorax of the moth appears grey and the posterior brown, with a coppery sheen. When the adults emerged then they were collected. This was made for 20 times development time period from egg to adult emergence for *P. interpunctella* was recorded.

Plate-1: Egg

Plate-2: Larvae

Plate-3:Pupal Formation

Plate-4: Pupa

Plate-5: Culture Box

Plate-6: Cellulae

Mass Rearing of Parasitoid *Bracon hebetor*

3.2.1 Introduction

Bracon hebetor Say (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) is an ecto-parasitoid that attacks the 4th–and 5th stage of pyralid moth larvae, including the greater wax moth (GWM) *Galleria mellonella*(L.) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) (Awadallah *et al.*, 1985). *Plodia interpunctella* (Hübner) (Milonas, 2005), *Corcyra cephalonica* (Stainton) (Krombeinet *et al.*, 1979), *Ephestia kuehniella* Zeller (Darwish *et al.*, 2003) and *Helicoverpa armigera* Hübner, *Heliothis virescens*(F.) (Attaran, 1996), that infest field crops as well as stored-products (Benson, 1974). The parasitoid is considered as a potential biological control agent of the lepidopteran stored product pests (Brower *et al.*, 1996) and also some field insect pests.

For many years, the management of lepidopteran pests has traditionally involved the use of fumigants, aerosols and other chemical insecticides. However, these moth species have become resistant to insecticides (Zettler *et al.*, 1973). Moreover, insecticides pose a direct risk to human health and the environment due to the presence of their residue in food products and in processing facilities where workers are exposed (Fields and White, 2002).

In recent years, interests have been focused for development of non-chemical strategies for insect control such as cultural, physical, biological, varietal, bio-rational and genetic control measures in place of conventional pesticides for the management of stored product insects as well as field pests. (Subramanyam and Hagsturm, 2000; Phillips, 2006). Of these strategies, the use of natural enemies, including parasitoids and predators is an important component of IPM and has many advantages over chemical control (Scholler *et al.*, 1997; Scholler and Flinn, 2000).

Bracon hebetor females paralyze their host larvae first by stinging and then variable numbers of eggs are laid on or near the surface of paralyzed hosts

(Antolin *et al.*, 1995). The paralyzed larvae of host are then used as food sources for developing larvae and also for the adult females (Doten, 1911; Richards and Thomson, 1932). Ghimire and Phillips (2010) studied the mass rearing of *B. hebetor* on *P. interpunctella* to observe the effects of host density, parasitoid density and the rearing containers size on adult progeny production and the sex ratio. They found that host density, parasitoid density and rearing container size had significant effect on adult progeny production but no effect on sex ratio.

The increasing attention for environmental safety and global demand for pesticide free food necessitated the search for eco-friendly methods of pest management. As a result, interest in biological control has increased considerably as a response to the various effects of pesticides on the environment and as a result of new international trends, which favours conservation and the sustainable use of biological resources. Researchers on biological control have recognized interactions between parasitoid and host to ensure the success of biological control programs.

Bracon hebetor (Say) is considered one of the potential biological control agents; it is a gregarious ecto-parasitoid, which completes its larval development on different species of Lepidoptera host larvae, especially larvae of Pyralidae (Lepidoptera) larvae, and having been introduced in successful IPM programs. Most of the species of Pyralidae are agricultural pests on some field crops and storage crops. The most important species of those insect pests are *Ephestia kuehniella* (Z.), *E. cautella* (Walk), *Galleria mellonella* (L.), *Achroi agrisella* (F.), *Helocover paarmigera*, *Corcyra cephalonica* and *Plodia interpunctella* (L) (Calderon *et al.*, 197; Brower *et al.*, 1996).

The efficiency of biological control depends upon the ability of the production of relatively inexpensive biological control agents of insect pests. The production of beneficial insects, especially parasitoids, has improved substantially in recent

years. The life table is one of the tools, used in quantitative analysis and in estimation of populations. So the present study was mainly focused on the effect of different hosts on the developmental time, longevity, fecundity and life table parameters of *B. hebetor*. The aim was to find the most suitable hosts for rearing *B. hebetor* to use as effective biological control agent.

3.2.2 Materials and Methods

Insect colony: A laboratory culture of *Bracon hebetor* was used for this experiment. Our initial *B. hebetor* culture was obtained from the post-harvest Entomology laboratory, Department of zoology, Rajshahi University. This laboratory culture was from adults collected from BARI at Joydevpur, Dhaka. They were reared on Indian meal moth larvae under laboratory condition at 25°C degree Celsius and 70-75% RH at the Post Harvest Entomology laboratory, Department of Zoology, Rajshahi University.

Culture box: For this experiment plastic boxes were used which were obtained from the local market. The height and width of the boxes were 9.50 cm and 15 cm respectively. Middle portion of the lid of the boxes were cut down and very small mesh size net was used there. This system allowed easy to gaseous exchange. The gap between lid and net were sealed very carefully so that a single larva will not come out outside from the culture box.

Diet: Indian meal moth larvae were used as the food of *B. hebetor*. The maize seed was collected from the laboratory. The larvae should be separated from the maize flour. It should be clean and free from net which is made by the Indian meal moth larvae.

Adult release: At least 7-10 pairs (7-10 males and 7-10 females of *B. hebetor*) were released in each mass culture box which was carrying at least 100 Indian

meal moth larvae. All the adults were fresh and newly hatched. In the box, baspata papers were placed on the box so that adults female can easily sit and lay eggs on it. Each female laid eggs till 5-7 days or more till they death. Males were died soon after mating and females were died after finishing the egg laying. When the last adult died in the mass culture box then we removed the dead bodies carefully from the boxes.

Emergence of *Bracon* Larva: After 3-4 days of releasing adults in the mass culture box, matured larvae were found in the culture box. The larvae of *Bracon* take food from the infested larvae of Indian meal moth. The larvae of *Bracon* take at least 1-2 days to reach in pupal stage.

Pupae: The larvae pupate either in a silken cocoon or unprotected. The pupae are 1.5 to 2.5mm in length and white in color. Pupation takes place away from the infested material. In fact, late instar larvae can travel such distances that they are often mistaken for clothing pests. The pupal stage lasts for 5-6days.

Adult collection: Adults are about 1/2 inch (12.7 mm) long with a wing span of about 5/8 inch (16 to 20 mm). The forewings of this moth are reddish brown with a copper sheen on the outer two thirds and grey on the inner third. At rest the wings are held roof-like over the body. The head and thorax of the moth appears grey and the posterior brown, with a coppery sheen. When the adults emerged then they were collected. This was made for 20 times development time period from egg to adult emergence for *P. interpunctella* was recorded.

Plate-1: Male *Bracon*

Plate-2: Female *Bracon*

Plate-3: *Bracon* culture

Plate-4: *Bracon* larvae

Plate-5: *Bracon* pupae

Plate-6: *Bracon* adult

Chapter Four

Photoperiod induction *Habrobracon Hebetor* (say.) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) Rearing Lepidopteran host *Corcyra Cephalonica* stainton.

Introduction

The rice moth *Corcyra cephalonica* stainton is an important insect pest of different stored products in tropics. It is the major pest of rice, wheat, sorghum, corn (maize), cocoa, peanuts, almonds, dates, groundnut, cotton seeds, coffee, spices and cocoa beans, cashews, raisins and millet (Cox et al., 1981; Trematerra, 1983; Allotey and kumar, 1985; Mbata, 1989; Allotey, 1991a; Johnson et al., 1992; Locatelli and Limuata, 1988; Harita et al., 2000).

Habrobracon hebetor is an ectoparasitoid of the larvae of many pyralid pest-species, that attack stored grains. The parasitoid is considered to have a potential for the biological control, of many other lepidopterous pests, of various crops, because it is highly aggressive. It occurs, naturally, throughout the world. There is a growing evidence that *B. hebetor* can also be an important bio-control agent of *Helicoverpa armigera*. It is used in Turkmenistan, on cotton and to a lesser extent, in Uzbekistan, where, they rely more on *Trichogramma pintoi*. It attacks the larval stage of stored grain pyralid moths, such as *Plodia interpunctella* Hilbner.

The biology of *H. hebetor* has been intensively studied because of its importance as a biological control agent of the moths and also it is easy to rear in the laboratory (Benson, 1973, Taylor, 1988; Brower and press, 1990; Heimpel et al, 1997; baker nad Fabric, 2000; Darwish et al., 2003; Giindiiz and Giilel, 2005; Milonas, 2005; Margo et al., 2006; Giindiiz et al., 2008). Many researchers have been studied on the effects of host quality and or quantity on biology and ecology of *H. hebetor* (Ullyett, 1945; Doust, 1959; Taylor, 1988; Yu et al, 2003).

Materials and Method:

Host culture:

The adults of Indian meal moth *C. Cephalonica* were collected from the local food facilities located at Rajshahi Metropolitan City. A laboratory culture of *C. Cephalonica* was used for this experiment. Our initial *C. Cephalonica* culture was obtained from the Post-Harvest Entomology Laboratory, Department of Zoology, Rajshahi University. They were reared on maize flour under the laboratory condition at 25 °C and 70-75% RH at the Post Harvest Entomology Laboratory, Department of Zoology, Rajshahi University.

Parasitoid culture:

The larval parasitoid *H. hebetor* was collected from Bangladesh Agriculture Research Institute (BARI), Gazipur in Dhaka. The parasitoid was reared in laboratory room at 25-27°C and 60-70% R.H at the Post Harvest Entomology Laboratory, Department of Zoology, Rajshahi University.